

BO'LADIGAN TEBRANISHLARNI BINOGA TA'SIRINI ANIQLASH VA KAMAYTIRISH CHORALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

Abdunazarov Akbarjon Shamsuddin o'g'li

Namangan muxandislik-qurilish instituti stajyor-taqqiqotchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7066654>

Annotatsiya. Maqolada avtomobillar harakati natijasida yo'llardan tarqalayotgan tebranishlarni turar joy va jamoat binolariga ta'siri o'rganish yo'nalish bo'yicha tarqalish tezligi va ularni kamaytirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: avtomobil yo'llari, tebranish, chekli elementlar, Plaxis 3D, tunnellar, ko'priklar.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ПО ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЮ И СНИЖЕНИЮ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ВИБРАЦИЙ АВТОТРАНСПОРТА НА ЗДАНИЕ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МЕСТНОГО СЫРЬЯ (КАМЫША)

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается влияние дорожных вибраций на жилые и общественные здания, скорость распространения и меры по их снижению.

Ключевые слова: автомобильные дороги, вибрация, конечные элементы, Plaxis 3D, тоннели, мосты.

IMPROVEMENT OF MEASURES TO DETERMINE AND REDUCE THE IMPACT OF VEHICLE VIBRATIONS ON THE BUILDING USING LOCAL RAW MATERIALS (CANE)

Abstract. The article examines the impact of road vibrations on residential and public buildings, the rate of propagation and measures to reduce them.

Keywords: highways, vibration, finite elements, Plaxis 3D, tunnels, bridges.

KIRISH

Avtomobillar harakati natijasida hosil bo'ladigan zararli tebranishlarni bino va inshootlarga ta'sirini o'rganish bo'yicha xorijda O.A.Shutov, A.B.Ponomarev, I.Y.Sukernikov, M.A.Dashevskiy, V.A.Smirnov, Hongzhen Vang, Chunsheng Zhang, Jianqun Jiang, Vey Huang, Dechang Guo, Tao Sheng, O.Y.Shexter, V.A.Ilichev, Y.K.Borisov, Avtomobillar yo'llaridagi asosidagi grunt turiga bog'liq xollarda tebranishlarni tarqalishi bo'yicha S.G.Alimov, A.G.Usov, L.G.Lisak, T.V.Krilova, Y.A.Stepanovlar va boshqa olimlar tomonidan tadqiqotlar o'tkazilgan.

Respublikamizda Sh.S.Yuldashev, B.Mardanov, Y.N.Muborakov, M.M.Mirsaidov, K.S.Sultonov, T.R.Rashidov, A.A.Ishanxodjayev, G'.X.Xojmetov, P.J.Matkarimov, Z.S.Buzrukoy, M.Karabayeva va M.B.Boytemirovlar tomonidan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari olib borilgan.

1-rasm: Plaxis 3D dasturida binoning konstruksiyasi va avtomagistral yo'lda avtomobil harakatlanishi

TADQIQOT MATERIALLARI VA METODOLOGIYASI

Bugungi kunda ushbu yo'nalishda olib borilgan keng ko'lamdagi tadqiqotlarga qaramasdan tebranishlarni kamaytirishda mahalliy xom ashyo turi qamishdan foydalanib ko'rilmagan.

2-rasm: Plaxis 3D dasturida binoga berilgan yukar

Avtomobillar harakati natijasida hosil bo'ladigan tebranishlar gruntida tarqalishining darajasini o'zgarishini sonli xisoblash usulini takomillashtirish orqali avtomobil yo'li yaqinida joylashgan ko'p qavatli bino va inshootlardagi tebranishlarni, qavatlar soniga bo'g'liqlik darajasini aniqlandi.

3-rasm: Plaxis 3D dasturida mesh qilish jarayoni

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Tebranishlar darajasini kamaytirish uchun gruntida joylashtirilgan mahalliy xom ashyolarni geometrik o'lchamlarini aniqlash va ularning samaradorligini baholash usullarini ishlab chiqish orqali avtomobillar yo'llaridagi tebranishlarni chekli elementlar usuli Plaxis 3D dasturida aniqlandi.

4-rasm: Plaxis 3D dasturida xisoblash jarayoni.

MUHOKAMA

Avtomobillar harakati natijasida hosil bo'ladigan tebranishlarni grunda va bino va inshootlarning konstruksiyalarida tarqalishi, ularning mexanik xususiyatlarini xisobga olgan holda sonli xisoblash usulini ishlab chiqqan xolda avtomobil yo'llari bino va inshootlarga, tarixiy yodgorliklar bilan birga tarixiy obidalarga nisbatan joylashish mavqeyini xisobga olib, avtomobillar harakatidan hosil bo'ladigan tebranishlarning grunda tarqalish jarayonini tadqiq qilindi.

4-rasm: Plaxis 3D dasturida Avtomobilning xarakatlanishi.

Tadqiqot jarayonida tizimli tahlil, grunlar mexanikasi, elastiklik nazariyasi, sonli usullar, chekli elementlar usullarining fundamental qonun va qoidalari, tajriba o'tkazish usullaridan foydalanildi.

XULOSA

Avtomobillar harakati natijasida yuzaga keladigan tebranishlarning tarqalishini tahlil qilish PLAXIS 3D yordamida chekli elementlar usulida amalga oshirildi, xulosa qilib aytganda mahalliy hom ashyolardan foydalanish iqtisodiy samaradorligi va qolgan tebra so'ndirgichlardan ancha afzalligi ham aniqlandi.

4-rasm: Avtomobil harakatlanishi natijasida hosil bo'ladigan zo'riqishlar

REFERENCES

1. Abdunazarov A., Soliev N. tudy of the performance of frameless construction structures under the influence of vertical stresses of ultra-submerged the lyoss soils //Студенческий вестник. – 2020. – Т. 28. – №. 126 часть 3. – С. 39.
2. 1. Хакимов С. АКТИВ ВА ПАССИВ СЕЙСМИК УСУЛЛАРИ ҲАМДА УЛАРНИНГ АСОСИЙ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ //Журнал интегрированного образования и исследований. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 30-36.
3. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
4. 2. Ильичев В. А., Юлдашев Ш. С., Саидов С. М. Исследование распространения вибрации при прохождении поездов в зависимости от расположения железнодорожного полотна //Основания, фундаменты и механика грунтов. – 1999. – №. 2. – С. 12-13.
5. 3. Yuldashev S. S., Boytemirov M. Influence of the level of the location of the railway canvas on the propagation of waves from train motion // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 05 (85). – 2020. – С. 140-143.
6. 4. Yuldashev S. S., Karabaeva M. U. Soil surface vibrations in the training of metro trains in parallel tunnels // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 05 (85). – 2020. – С. 117-121.

7. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 13-19.
8. 5. Mirsaidov M., Boytemirov M., Yuldashev F. Estimation of the Vibration Waves Level at Different Distances // Proceedings of FORM 2021. – Springer, Cham, 2022. – С. 207-215.
9. 6. Yuvmitov A., Hakimov S. R. Influence of seismic isolation on the stress-strain state of buildings //Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 71-79.
10. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 1-5.
11. 7. Ювмитов А. С., Хакимов С. Р. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ СЕЙСМОИЗОЛЯЦИИ НА ДИНАМИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЗДАНИЯ //Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 14.